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PROJECT MANAGEMENT GUIDELINES

General information

Project name	AgroServ Integrated services supporting a sustainable agroecological transition
Deliverable	D9.1 PROJECT MANAGEMENT GUIDELINES
Work package	WP9
Grant agreement n°	101058020
Call	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01
Project duration	01.09.2022 - 31.08.2027 (60 months)
Project coordinator	Michel Boër michel.boer@anaee.eu
Dissemination level	Public
Deliverable main authors	Sarah Dramé sarah.drame@anaee.eu
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Due submission date	30/11/2022
Actual submission date	30/11/2022
Dissemination level	PU
Status	Accepted by the REA

Quality of information — Disclaimer

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Version history

Version n°	Date	Description	Authors
V1.0	30/11/2022	First version of the guidelines, overview of how the consortium works together	Sarah Dramé, Michel Boër
V2.0	29/04/24	Updated template, mistake correction, improvement of text	Sarah Dramé

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Executive Summary

The AgroServ Project Management Guidelines aim to provide a structured approach to organizing, planning, and overseeing the AgroServ project, with the goal of maximizing the project's success. These guidelines are designed to address every aspect of the project at the right time and level of detail, based on the project's scale and complexity.

The guide includes essential information on management strategy, the structure of the consortium, reporting requirements, document templates, publication protocols, and more. It also seeks to explain the legal and financial aspects of the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement to ensure all stakeholders have a clear understanding.

This guide is intended to be flexible and adaptable, evolving as needed throughout the lifecycle of the AgroServ project. It will be updated periodically to reflect any significant changes or new information. Each time an update occurs, all partners will be promptly notified of the changes and how they differ from previous versions.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The AgroServ Project Management Guidelines aim to help organize, plan, and control the project effectively. These guidelines are designed to maximize the project's chances of success by addressing each element at the appropriate time and in the right level of detail, based on the project's size and complexity.

The guidelines cover essential knowledge related to management strategy, consortium structure, reporting issues, templates, publication procedures, and more. They also clarify the legal and financial aspects of the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement for beneficiaries and affiliated parties.

This guide is dynamic and can be updated as needed throughout the project's lifecycle. Updates will include new information, relevant issues, and changes in procedures. Each time the document is revised, all partners will be informed about the updates and changes made from the previous version.

1.2 Applicable and Reference documents

Applicable Documents:

- AD1: Grant Agreement
 - Grant Agreement with the European Commission: Grant Agreement No. 101058020.
- AD2: Consortium Agreement (CA)
 - The Consortium Agreement signed, accepted, and approved by all partners on 18/11/2022.

Reference Documents:

- RD1: The Proposal
 - Available only to the parties of the Consortium Agreement.

2. Project main data

2.1 Participating institutions

The lists of the beneficiaries, affiliated entities and associated legal entities are given in appendix 2 at the end of the document.

2.2 Project duration, budget and EC Contribution

The project officially starts on September 1, 2022, and will end 60 months later, on August 31, 2027. It has a total budget of €14,252,873.35, funded by the European Commission.

The budget for each beneficiary and the corresponding EU contribution are detailed in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement, titled "Estimated Budget of the Action."

The EU contribution for each partner is a maximum amount, contingent on the European Commission's acceptance of the partner's expenses up to their allocated budget. If a partner spends less than their approved budget or if the Commission does not accept all their costs, the partner will only receive a proportional part of the EU contribution.

3. Work packages and deliverables

The overall project plan follows the tasks, activities, and schedule outlined in the Work Plan (Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement). The focus of all work and planning will be on the deliverables due to the European Commission during the four reporting periods (RPs) of AgroServ:

- RP1: Month 1 to Month 12 (01/09/2022 - 31/08/2023)
- RP2: Month 13 to Month 28 (01/09/2023 - 31/12/2024)
- RP3: Month 29 to Month 44 (01/01/2025 - 30/04/2026)
- RP4: Month 45 to Month 60 (01/05/2026 - 31/08/2027)

3.1 Work package overview

AgroServ is a 60-month project organized in the following Work Packages:

Work Package No	Work Package name	Lead Beneficiary	Effort (Person-Months)	Start Month	End Month
WP1	Integrated joint management framework for TNA	11 - FZJ	111.00	1	60
WP2	AgroServ integration and customisation of services	3 - CIHEAM-IAMB	97.60	1	60
WP3	Consolidating integrated data management and analysis services	28 - ELIXIR/EMBL	94.30	1	60
WP4	Access quality management & Ethics	17 - INRAE	77.50	1	58
WP5	Community building and users' engagement	30 - LifeWatch ERIC	96.00	1	60
WP6	Open Innovation Hub	33 - ENEA	85.40	4	56
WP7	Developing a roadmap for long-term sustainability beyond 2027	6 - AnaEE ERIC	25.03	25	60
WP8	Outreach, dissemination, exploitation of results	1 - CNRS	47.48	1	60
WP9	Project Management and monitoring	1 - CNRS	139.05	1	60
WP10	TA1 EMPHASIS	11 - FZJ	115.12	13	60
WP11	TA2 AnaEE	6 - AnaEE ERIC	129.18	13	60
WP12	TA/VA1 EMBRC	20 - EMBRC-ERIC	2.90	13	60
WP13	TA/VA2 SmartCow	17 - INRAE	117.05	13	60
WP14	TA3 Metrofood-RI	33 - ENEA	60.80	13	60
WP15	TA4 IBISBA	17 - INRAE	44.20	13	60
WP16	TA/VA3 Euro-BioImaging	28 - ELIXIR/EMBL	31.37	13	60
WP17	TA5 EU-OPENSREEN	22 - EU-OS	29.22	13	60
WP18	TA6 MIRRI	17 - INRAE	30.84	13	60
WP19	VA1 ELIXIR	28 - ELIXIR/EMBL	30.01	13	60
WP20	VA2 LifeWatch	30 - LifeWatch ERIC	75.00	12	60
WP21	TA7 Socioeconomics	10 - UTAD	136.67	12	60

Table 1: *Work Package organization*

Figure 1: *Synergy and collaboration between WP1 -WP9 to achieve project goals*

The detailed description of each Work Package is provided in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, titled "List of Work Packages." Each Work Package (WP) is led by a designated WP Leader, who is the partner responsible for managing and coordinating the technical and economic aspects of the Work Package.

- The WP Leader's responsibilities include:
- Preparing technical reports
- Achieving milestones and deliverables
- Providing deliverables to the coordinator on schedule
- Submitting interim and progress reports to the coordinator on schedule

Each partner involved in a Work Package must appoint a specific individual to serve as the Work Package Leader.

WP	Name	Role	Institution
1	Roland Pieruschka	WP leader	Forschungszentrum Jülich (EMPHASIS)
1	Heba Ibrahim	Central Access Manager	
2	Ivana Cavoski	WP leader	CIHEAM BARI (AnaEE)
2	Tiziana Tota	Substitute	
3	Cyril Pommier	WP leader	ELIXIR
3	Katharina Heil	Substitute	
4	René Baumont	WP leader	SmartCow (INRAE)
4	Alex Mc Dougall	Substitute	
5	Iria Soto	WP leader	LifeWatch ERIC
5	Jose Manuel Avila	Substitute	
6	Claudia Zoani	WP leader	ENEA (METROFOOD)
6	Diana Garcia Bernet	Substitute	
7	Ogheneyoma Olisah	WP leader	AnaEE-ERIC
7	Jose Manuel Avila	Substitute	
8	Daniele Baldo	WP leader	AnaEE-ERIC
9	Sarah Dramé	WP leader	AnaEE-ERIC

Table 2: *Work Package Leaders*

3.2 Deliverable

Each WP will have associated deliverables. All deliverables are rigorously tracked throughout the AgroServ project by the project manager. The complete list of deliverables for the 60-month project is provided next, arranged in chronological order to facilitate easy tracking of submission deadlines and submitted to all WPs. For deliverables that have multiple versions without fixed submission dates, only the initial delivery is listed. Partners responsible for these deliverables must ensure timely submission of all required versions. The Project Officer (PO) will be informed of any delay prior the deadline via the European Commission's Participant Portal platform, Sygma.

3.3 Procedure for the submission of the deliverable:

Throughout the project, deliverables identified in Appendix 3 (related to Annex 1, list of deliverables to the Grant Agreement) must be completed and submitted to the European Commission (EC) according to the timetable specified in Appendix 3. All deliverables must be submitted electronically via the Participant Portal. Task leaders and Work Package (WP) leaders are responsible for the technical quality of the deliverables.

The internal procedure for submitting a deliverable is as follows:

- The deliverable is reviewed internally within the relevant Work Package(s) (WP) members.

- The relevant WP coordinator sends the draft deliverable to the Coordination Team (CT), which includes the Project Coordinator (PC) and the European Project Manager (EPM). The Management Board will appoint 2 members of the Executive Committee (ExCom) as reviewers of said deliverable.
- The deliverable is then submitted to the reviewers for feedback for 1 week. In the case there are elements that require modification, the deliverable will be sent back to the WP leader for revision.
- Once the extended management board approves the deliverable, the EMP submits the deliverable to the REA.

The REA then examines the deliverable and may approve it, reject it, or request changes.

To ensure timely submission to the REA, WP leaders must submit their deliverables no later than 2 weeks before the due date. The CT will evaluate the deliverables diligently to avoid delays and allow for necessary revisions.

If any delays are detected, they should be reported to the Project Coordinator immediately. This will allow for corrective actions and ensure the EC Project Officer (PO) is informed. Delays in deliverables may require an amendment to the Grant Agreement (GA).

Figure 2: Deliverable submission timeframe

Figure 3: AgroServ management structure

The role of the various AgroServ bodies is defined the CA and reproduced in appendix 5.

4.2 Project Management Procedures

General Management Procedures:

Partner Responsibilities:

- Ensure effective economic management and conduct operational work according to program guidelines, ethical standards, and legal requirements.
- Comply with the general and specific terms and conditions of each grant or granting program established by the European Commission.
- Manage and supervise operational personnel.
- Meet the reporting requirements specific to Horizon Europe and the call, acknowledging the coordinator's financial support when possible.

Decision-Making Mechanism:

- Decisions must be taken at the appropriate decision-making level.
- Roles and responsibilities of each Consortium body are defined in the project Consortium Agreement.
- Consensus is the preferred method of approbation within each Consortium body, otherwise vote.

Meetings:

- Consortium bodies meet regularly to discuss progress, exchange information, and share results.
- Meetings can be held via video conferences or other communication means.
- Use provided templates to keep agendas, attendance lists, and minutes, and store them in the collaborative folders.

Monitoring and Progress Reporting:

- Each partner and WP leader will report project progress to the European Project Manager (EPM).
- Reports will cover technical progress, results, deliverables, compliance with the WP schedule, and risk monitoring and updates.
- The Project Coordinator will support the EPM in the process and in reviewing legal and administrative aspects.
- The progress report will be validated by the Executive Board before being sent to the European Commission.

5. Information Management

5.1. Document Management

The document management procedures ensure that project documents are produced, updated, distributed, and stored efficiently and correctly. The official documentation repository for the AgroServ project is accessible through NextCloud, with public documents also available on the project website.

To gain access to the NextCloud, an account will be created by requesting access to the EPM.

Key Points of Document Management:

- Repository Access: All project documents are managed via the NextCloud application.
- Organization and Content Summary:
 - Contractual Documents: Includes the Grant Agreement with the European Commission and its annexes, as well as the Consortium Agreement and its annexes.
 - Financial & Administrative Guidelines: Contains Horizon Europe guidelines and recommendations.
 - Contact List: Provides access to the complete contact list of project partners.
 - Templates: Offers access to updated and official project templates.
 - External Communications: Includes leaflets, roll-ups, photos, and other materials.
 - Collaborative Agendas: Shared agendas for collaborative work.
 - Meetings and Events: Links to project-level meetings and events pages.
 - WP Gantt Chart: Work Package (WP) timelines and schedules.
 - WP Internal Documents: Internal documents related to each WP.
 - WP Deliverables: Deliverables for each WP.
 - Meeting Records: Includes records of General Assembly, Executive Board, and Management Board meetings.

These procedures ensure that all project documentation is well-organized, easily accessible, and up to date, facilitating smooth communication and collaboration among project partners.

5.2. Technical Information Flow Chart

The Work Package (WP) leaders and the European Project Manager (EPM) play crucial roles in managing the technical information within the project.

Information Transmission:

- All partners must continuously communicate relevant information to the WP Leader and the Coordination Team (CT).
- This includes project progress, WP meetings, updates to the common NextCloud calendar, and any relevant issues.
- Communication should occur on a daily basis.

Issue Management:

1. The WP Leader is responsible for addressing and resolving issues as they arise.
2. If an issue cannot be resolved by the WP Leader, it will be escalated to the EPM.
3. The EPM will either resolve the issue or escalate it to the Project Coordinator if necessary.
4. Any issues that significantly impact the project's work and planning will be promptly discussed with the Management Board.

This process ensures efficient handling of technical information and quick resolution of issues, maintaining smooth project operations. During this process, advice from the PO may be requested by the PC and/or the EPM.

5.3. Administrative Information Flow

Definition: Administrative information includes any information related to the project's administrative procedures, including financial matters and beneficiary details.

Procedure:

Any changes in administrative information, such as legal details, organization name changes, or changes in authorized representatives, must be promptly communicated to the European Project Manager (EPM) and the Project Coordinator.

Use the provided templates to report these changes and ensure necessary measures are taken.

5.4. Templates

Usage:

All official AgroServ documents (e.g., presentations, deliverables, external communications, meeting minutes) must use the designated templates.

Templates are available in NextCloud and may be updated over the course of the project.

Recommendation:

Always download the latest version of the template from NextCloud before creating a new document to ensure compliance with the most current standards. To obtain the latest templates, the communication officer can be contacted as well.

Standard documents

Please use the following labels for documents to ensure proper structuring on the collaboration platform, NextCloud.

Type	Label	Example
Emails	AgroServ + event/activity	AgroServ Kick-off meeting
Documents	YYMMDD_AgroServ_name of document	221130_AgroServ_Template
Deliverables	Deliverable.No_AgroServ_deliverable short name	D9.1_AgroServ_Project Handbook

Table 3: Document labelling

Communication Elements

A Communication Plan will be provided to each participant, outlining detailed guidelines for project communication. Here are some key elements to keep in mind:

Project Acronym and Logo:

- Always use the project acronym and logo together in all communications to ensure consistent and recognizable branding.
- Maintain the same design and placement for both elements to enhance visibility and coherence.

Social Media Awareness:

- To increase project visibility on social media, use the hashtag #AgroServ in all relevant posts and updates and tag the official pages on LinkedIn and X (@AgroServEU).
- This helps to create a unified and searchable presence across various platforms and allows the Communications officer to build a coherent strategy on social media.

Following these guidelines will help ensure that our project is consistently represented and easily identifiable across all communication channels.

Acknowledgement of EU Funding

To ensure proper acknowledgment of EU funding in all public documents, communications, and presentations, please adhere to the following guidelines, which are also detailed in the project's Brand Guidelines.

1. Displaying the EU Emblem:

- **EU Emblem Placement:** Include the EU emblem in all public documents, communications, and presentations.
- **Prominence:** When the EU emblem is displayed alongside other logos, it must have appropriate prominence, meaning it should be clearly visible and not overshadowed by other logos.
- **EU Emblem Source:** You can obtain the EU emblem from the official [EU website](#) and on the AgroServ NextCloud

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EU Logo Disclaimer: All documents produced within the project and using the EU logo must display the following disclaimer as displayed in the annex 5 of the GA:

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These procedures ensure that all relevant records are available for review and compliance purposes, maintaining transparency and accountability throughout and after the project.

2. AgroServ Logo:

- **Access to Logos:** AgroServ logos are available in the "communication" folder within the collaborative folders.
- **Brand Guidelines:** Ensure that the AgroServ logo is included in all project-related documents according to the graphic charter, which is available in the "communication" folder in the collaborative hub.

Payment Procedures

The European Commission (EC) contribution to the project is structured in several stages, each with specific conditions and timing:

1. Pre-Financing Payment:

Timing: Issued at the beginning of the project.

Purpose: To provide initial funding to cover the initial expenses and ensure that project activities can commence smoothly.

2. Second Pre-Financing Payment:

Timing: Issued after the successful submission and approval of the first internal report.

Conditions: The first internal report must meet the requirements set by the EC and demonstrate satisfactory progress.

Purpose: To support continued project activities and maintain momentum following the initial phase.

3. Interim Payments:

Timing: Two interim payments are scheduled throughout the project, aligned with the EC reporting periods.

Conditions: Payments are made based on the submission of interim reports, which must be approved by the EC. These reports should detail progress, expenditures, and adherence to the project plan.

Purpose: To provide ongoing financial support as the project progresses, helping to cover operational costs and ensure financial stability.

4. Final Payment:

Timing: Issued at the end of the project, following the final reporting period.

Conditions: The final payment is made after the submission and approval of the final report, which includes a comprehensive summary of project outcomes, expenditures, and achievements.

Purpose: To cover remaining project costs and conclude the financial aspect of the project.

Note: Each payment stage is contingent upon meeting specific reporting and performance criteria as outlined in the Grant Agreement. Timely and accurate submission of reports and adherence to project milestones are essential for receiving payments as scheduled.

Reporting and payment schedule (art 21, 22):

Reporting					Payments	
Reporting periods			Type	Deadline	Type	Deadline (time to pay)
RP No	Month from	Month to				
					Initial prefinancing	30 days from entry into force/10 days before starting date – whichever is the latest
1	1	12	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment	90 days from receiving periodic report
2	13	28	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment	90 days from receiving periodic report
3	29	44	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment	90 days from receiving periodic report
4	45	60	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Final payment	90 days from receiving periodic report

Table 4: Reporting and payment schedule table

6. Records

General Requirements:

Availability: Records and supporting documents must be readily available upon request, or as required during checks, reviews, audits, or investigations.

Retention During Procedures: If there are ongoing checks, reviews, audits, investigations, litigation, or claims related to the Agreement, beneficiaries must retain all records and supporting documentation until these procedures are complete.

Document Types and Retention Periods:

1. Confidentiality:

- **Retention Period:** 5 years after the final payment.
- **Description:** Documents containing sensitive or confidential information must be kept for this duration to protect privacy and proprietary information.

2. Record-Keeping:

Retention Period: 5 years after the final payment, or 3 years for grants of €60,000 or less.

Description: General project records and supporting documentation must be preserved for this period for potential future reference or verification.

3. Reviews:

Retention Period: Up to 2 years after the final payment.

Description: Records related to any reviews of the project must be kept for this duration.

4. Audits:

Retention Period: Up to 2 years after the final payment.

Description: Documentation related to audits must be retained for this period to allow for any post-audit queries or issues.

5. Extension of Findings from Other Grants:

Retention Period: No later than 2 years after the final payment.

Description: If findings from other grants are extended to this grant, the relevant documentation must be kept for this period.

6. Impact Evaluation:

Retention Period: Up to 5 years after the final payment.

Description: Documents related to the impact evaluation of the project should be retained for this duration to assess long-term outcomes and benefits.

Document Formats:

- Original Documents: Beneficiaries must keep original documents.
- Digital and Digitized Documents: Digital and digitized documents are considered originals if authorized by applicable national law.
- Non-Original Documents: The granting authority may accept non-original documents if they provide a comparable level of assurance as originals.

These procedures ensure that all relevant records are available for review and compliance purposes, maintaining transparency and accountability throughout and after the project.

Appendix 1:

Common Acronyms List

Acronyms	Full Name
AgroServ	Integrated services supporting a sustainable agroecological transition
AM	Access Manager
IM	Installation Manager
I	Installation
RI	Research Infrastructure
TA	Transnational Access
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ISIA	Information System for Infrastructure Administration
GDPR	General data protection regulation
CatRIS	Catalogue of Research Infrastructure Services
LL	Living Lab
AE	Agroecology
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EC	European Commission
REA	Research Executive Agency
ALLEA	ALL European Academies (federation of academies of sciences and humanities)
DPO	Data Protection Officer
Com	Communication Officer
CT	Coordinating Team (PC+EPM+Com)
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action (annex 1)
EPM	European Project Manager
ExeCom/ExCom	Executive Committee
GA	General Assembly
GA	Grant Agreement
IEAB	Independent Ethical Advisory Board
ManB	Management Board
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer (REA)

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REA	Research Executive Agency (EC)
RP	Reporting Period
SSAB	Science and Stakeholder Advisory Board
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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Appendix 2:

List of participants

	Participant organization name	Short	Country
1	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	CNRS	France
2	USTAV VYZKUMU GLOBALNI ZMENY AV CR VVI	UVGZ	Czechia
3	CENTRO INTERNAZIONALE DI ALTISTUDI AGRONOMICI MEDITERRANEI	CIHEAM-IAMB	Italy
4	LUONNONVARAKESKUS	LUKE	Finland
5	VYTAUTO DIDZIOJO UNIVERSITETAS	VDU	Lithuania
6	ANALYSIS AND EXPERIMENTATION ON ECOSYSTEMS ERIC	AnaEE ERIC	France
7	UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	ULIEGE	Belgium
8	UNIVERSITEIT ANTWERPEN	UANTWERPEN	Belgium
9	INSTITUTE OF SOIL SCIENCE, AGRO-TECHNOLOGY AND PLANT PROTECTION NIKOLA POUHKAROV	ISSAPPNP	Bulgaria
10	UNIVERSIDADE DE TRAS-OS-MONTES E ALTO DOURO	UTAD	Portugal
11	FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JÜLICH GMBH	FZJ	Germany
12	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	EV ILVO	Belgium
13	JULIUS KÜHN-INSTITUT BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FÜR KULTURPFLANZEN	JKI	Germany
14	THE HEBREW UNIVERSITY OF JERUSALEM	HUJI	Israel
15	AGENZIA LUCANA DI SVILUPPO E DI INNOVAZIONE IN AGRICOLTURA	ALSIA	Italy
16	INSTITUT ZA RATARSTVO I POVRTARSTVO INSTITUT OD NACIONALNOG ZNACAJA ZA REPUBLIKU SRBIJU	IFVCNS	Serbia

17	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	INRAE	France
18	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY	TEAGASC	Ireland
19	EURO-BIOIMAGING ERIC	EURO-BIOIMAGING	Finland
20	EUROPEAN MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CENTRE EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM	EMBRC-ERIC	France
21	UNIVERSITÉ CATHOLIQUE DE LOUVAIN	UCL	Belgium
22	EUROPEAN INFRASTRUCTURE OF OPEN SCREENING PLATFORMS FOR CHEMICAL BIOLOGY EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM	EU- OPENSREEN ERIC	Germany
23	WEIZMANN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE	WEIZMANN	Israel
24	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	ESF	France
25	FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FÜR NUTZTIERBIOLOGIE	FBN	Germany
26	UNIVERSITEIT HASSELT	UHASSELT	Belgium
27	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	Netherlands
28	EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY	ELIXIR/EMBL	Germany
29	UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA	UNL	Portugal
30	E-SCIENCE EUROPEAN INFRASTRUCTURE FOR BIODIVERSITY AND ECOSYSTEM RESEARCH	LifeWatch ERIC	Spain
31	CENTRE WALLON DE RECHERCHES AGRONOMIQUES	CRA-W	Belgium
32	INSTITUT DE RECERCA I TECNOLOGIA AGROALIMENTARIES	IRTA - CERCA	Spain
33	AGENZIA NAZIONALE PER LE NUOVE TECNOLOGIE, L'ENERGIA E LO SVILUPPO ECONOMICO SOSTENIBILE	ENEA	Italy
34	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE PENTRU BIORESURSE ALIMENTARE	IBA BUCUREȘTI	Romania

35	CESKA ZEMEDEL'SKA UNIVERZITA V PRAZE	CZU	Czechia
36	INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN	JSI	Slovenia
37	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	AU	Denmark
38	KØBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	UCPH	Denmark
39	CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA	CREA	Italy
40	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	CNR	Italy
41	ASSOCIACAO BIP4DAB	BioData	Portugal
42	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	WU	Netherlands

Appendix 3:

List of deliverables

You can access the list of deliverables and milestones via the [following link](#). Deliverables are indicated in green, while milestones are represented in grey. Please note that variations in shading may occur to enhance document readability.

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Appendix 4:

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Appendix 5:

The consortium various roles

Consortium Body	Responsibilities	Members	Periodicity of meetings
General Assembly (GA)	<p>The following decisions shall be taken by the General Assembly:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content, finances and intellectual property rights. Decisions regarding intellectual property rights and Exploitation will be made together with the Parties' Technology Transfer Offices. • Proposals for changes to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Granting Authority • Changes to the Consortium Plan • Modifications to Attachment 1 and additions to Attachment 3 and 4 (refer to the Consortium Agreement) • Entry of a new Party to the Project and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party • Withdrawal of a Party from the Project and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the withdrawal • Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under this Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement • Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party • Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party • Termination of a Defaulting Party's participation in the Project and measures relating thereto • Proposal to the Granting Authority for a change of the coordinator • Proposal to the Granting Authority for suspension of all or part of the Project 	<p>The General Assembly is composed of one representative of each Beneficiary and Associated Partner (see subsection 4.1) and is chaired by the Project Coordinator and supported by his Coordinator Team.</p>	<p>Once a year in person.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proposal to the Granting Authority for termination of the Project and the Consortium Agreement 		
Project Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under this Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement Keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority Transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned Administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks described in Section 7.2 Providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims. 	Michel Boër	
Executive Board (steering body)	<p>The Executive Committee shall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing Related data and deliverables Prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications and other communication activities. 	The Executive Committee is composed of representatives of the ESFRI RIs listed in the project: MIRRI, ELIXIR, Euro-Bioimaging,	The Executive Committee will meet 3 times per year (1 physical meeting and 2 virtual meetings).

		<p>EMPHASIS, AnaEE, EMBRC, MetroFood, IBISBA, Lifewatch, EU Openscreen, representative of Smart Cow starting community, representative of Social Science services, appointed by GA (UTAD or LUKE) and ESF as observer.</p>	
<p>Management Board</p>	<p>The Management Board shall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support of the coordinator in the operational management tasks. • Implementation of the decisions of GA and Exec Board. • Monitor progress of WG 1-9 and take appropriate actions. • Communication within WG 1-9 (project WGs). • Monitor KPIs. • Report to the Executive Committee prior to meetings and suggest an agenda. • Follow communication actions towards targeted public (science, stakeholders, etc.). • Preparation of calls, release, following output of relevant WPs, as well as advice from SSAB, and decisions by the ExCom. • Day-to-day management of the collaboration 	<p>ManB is composed by the Coordinator, the Work Package Leaders (WP 1-9)</p>	<p>For the first year of the project, the ManB will meet once a month by videoconferencing. In case of urgent matters, the ManB can meet exceptionally, or can take decisions by email. In-person meeting twice a year.</p>

WP Leaders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate all technical tasks and activities and ensure coherence with the work plan • Maintain monthly contact with task leaders • Review and approve results, deliverables and milestones • Submit results, deliverables and milestones to the ExCom and ManB • Inform the EPM about new results and knowledge inform immediately the coordinator in case of risks or delay 	See the AgroServ management structure image	WP meetings will take place once a month.
European Project Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assist the coordinator and consortium in financial, administrative and legal matters • Organize day-to-day management and meetings • Provide templates and guidelines 	Sarah Dramé	
External Board of the consortium			
Advisory Board	<p><u>SSAB</u>: External independent experts representing the scientific and academic community and stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assist and facilitate the decisions made by the General Assembly. • Assess the quality of the scientific deliverables according to the state-of-the-art and the Work Plan defined in Annex 1 of the GA. • The SSAB will assemble regularly and will report to the Management Board. 	Alexander Wezel; Gerald Schwarz; Giulia Campodonic o ; Torsten Rodel Berg	Officially invited to special workshops/sessions/board meetings.
	<p>IEAB: external independent experts; appointed by ExCom.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advice on ethical issues connected to research in AgroServ and providing guidelines to be implemented by the Operational Ethics Committee. 	TBA	Officially invited to special workshops/sessions/board meetings.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Evaluate also how ethical issues have been dealt, and progress achieved.		
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Appendix 6:

Common Glossary

Term	Definition
Access	Access to the research infrastructures under the project AgroServ is provided free of charge to the User/User Groups once their proposals for the use of services have been approved and passed the eligibility criteria, and the feasibility and scientific evaluations during the selection phases. For more details see D1.3 AgroServ Access Policy.
Access Manager	Manager of access and service provision in a Research Infrastructure (list of Access Managers Appendix 1 of D1.2).
Access Provider	Manage of a specific facility or service within an organisation that is a member of a Research infrastructure.
AgroServ	The present project providing integrated services to support the sustainable agroecological transition.
Catalogue	The customer-facing list and description of all current installations, Services and Resources that can be offered by AgroServ RI to users. It is a subset of the Portfolio.
Data Management Plan	Guidelines for management of data within AgroServ.
Experiment	A planned activity carried out by partners of a project, who are USERS, i.e., a group of persons who uses one or more facilities.
Facility.	Cf. Installation.
Installation	Facility or installation (used as synonyms) required for the implementation of a specific service, usually users obtain access to experimental providing specific services (experimentation, data analysis etc.).
Research Infrastructure	Facilities or installation that provide resources and services for the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. For more details see D1.3 AgroServ Access Policy.
Resource	Any physical or digital asset or infrastructure made available to Users. Resources are generally tangible (concrete) elements and most of the time do not require an instantiation. Resources include instruments, equipment, data(sets), software, biological samples, etc.
Service	The mean or a process a user employs to deliver results. Services are usually intangible although they may also include tangible elements, since it relies on a set of resources. Services require instantiation by a Service Provider.

	Services include experimentations, observations, analysis, modelling, compute, data and material storage, training, consultancy, etc.
Trans-National/Virtual Access	Trans-National and Virtual Access allowing third-party researchers from a foreign institution to access an organisation's research facilities (installations) and services (TA) and access to an organisation's cloud, data centre, and/or its other IT facilities and services such as data analysis/analysis pipeline set-up or other more "operational" components.
User or User Group	The external committer of resources that exploits the transnational or virtual access services offered by the AgroServ project; the user can be an individual or a team of researchers from the public or private sector.
Work Package	A set working group of related activities within a project.